

Guidelines for the Publication of Cultural Data for AI Research

Version 1.0 (July 2025)

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Introduction

Large volumes of suitable data form the necessary basis for the development, optimisation and evaluation of AI processes. However, digital and freely reusable data collections of relevant size, quality and diversity are still largely lacking, especially in the area of historical cultural data. Digitised cultural data can close an important gap here. However, it is important to ensure that the digital collections and metadata are also made available to researchers in the formats relevant to AI development, with an appropriate documentation and on appropriate platforms, so that making them available can in turn trigger new innovations in AI research. These innovations successively ensure that new offerings are also created for those institutions that are not directly involved in AI research themselves.

These guidelines provide a comprehensive introduction to the creation of cultural datasets for AI research, introduce specific tools, methods and strategies for the publication of cultural data and emphasise the importance of transparency, documentation and quality assurance. The handbook is aimed at cultural heritage institutions and funding authorities and presents comprehensive recommendations for improving the provision and use of AI-compatible cultural heritage datasets. It was developed at the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin – Preußischer Kulturbesitz as part of the research project “Human.Machine.Culture”¹ which was funded by the Federal Government Commissioner for Culture and the Media (BKM).

The mass digitisation that has taken place in galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) in recent decades has created the conditions for open access to Collections as Data.² This enables new possibilities for researching, utilising and reusing digital collections. GLAM Labs³ at research and cultural heritage institutions⁴ are strong advocates of Collections as Data and show numerous examples of the publication of datasets under open licences, as well as the reuse of digital content in the (creative) economy. We are currently in a phase of transition towards emerging data spaces,⁵ cultural heritage clouds⁶ and open access.⁷

¹ <https://mmk.sbb.berlin/>.

² Padilla, T., Allen, L., Frost, H., Potvin, S., Roke, E., & Varner, S. (2022). *Always Already Computational: Collections as Data*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/MX6UK>; Chambers, S., Walsh, Melanie, Caswell, Michelle, Harder, Geoff, Okumura, Mercedes, Corrin, Julia, Baeza Ventura, Gabriela, Antonijevic, Smiljana, Knazook, Beth, Narlock, Mikala, Bailey, Jefferson, Neudecker, Clemens, Downie, J. Stephen, Layne-Worthey, Glen, van Strien, Daniel, Irollo, Alba, Whitmire, Amanda, Lee, James, Berry, Dorothy, ... Ridge, Mia. (2023). *Position Statements -> Collections as Data: State of the field and future directions*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7897735>.

³ <https://glamlabs.io/>.

⁴ Kokegei, K., Karner, S., Potter, A., Laursen, D., Wagner, S.-C., Straube, A., Wilms, L., Mahey, M., Ames, S., Al-Abdulla, A., Candela, G., Bray, P., Derven, C., Chambers, S., Gasser, K., & Dobрева-McPherson, M. (2019). *Open a GLAM Lab*. Alicante: Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes, 2021. <https://www.cervantesvirtual.com/nd/ark:/59851/bmc1066245>.

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/deployment-common-european-data-space-cultural-heritage>.

⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en.

⁷ https://www.dfg.de/foerderung/programme/infrastruktur/lis/open_access/.

The demand for such data is determined on the one hand by users, particularly from the field of digital humanities, who are interested in full texts of historical works for text and data mining, for example, and on the other hand by advances in the field of machine learning and artificial intelligence. Typical applications for digital cultural heritage include text recognition,⁸ information extraction from full texts⁹ and machine-assisted cataloguing.¹⁰ Currently, most machine learning applications are based on neural networks that are trained on large amounts of data. Models that are trained with poor or incorrect data cannot deliver high-quality results: ‘garbage in – garbage out’. The capabilities of these machine learning models therefore depend to a large extent on the type and quality of the data used to train them. However, it is often not clear where the data used to train the models come from and what undesirable effects statistical and content biases in the data have on the resulting models.¹¹ Therefore, if cultural heritage institutions adopt machine-learning applications and models from industry, particular care must be taken because, with few exceptions, these models have been trained on contemporary data from the internet and therefore the data distribution on which the models are applied usually differs significantly from the data distribution of the training data. If collections from the cultural heritage sector are to be made available as data and increasingly used to train and fine-tune¹² machine learning models, then it is highly desirable to establish a curatorial process aimed at identifying, documenting and contextualising problematic content (e.g. resulting from colonialism, racism or underrepresentation of marginalised groups) due to the predominantly historical nature of the data which result from, e.g., the digitisation of collections. From this from today's perspective problematic content will be reflected in machine learning models that have been trained with such data.

Overall, the endeavour to offer Collections as Data poses serious challenges in particular for small and medium-sized cultural heritage institutions. However, there is already a broad body of literature on this topic, which is also cited in this guide. In addition to the aforementioned publications of the US-American Collections as Data project, the report “Machine Learning + Libraries”,¹³ which lists a number of challenges for the conception, planning and implementation of machine learning projects, should be mentioned here. These challenges include the top priority of creating machine-readable datasets. This

⁸ Reul, C., Springmann, U., Wick, C., & Puppe, F. (2018). State of the Art Optical Character Recognition of 19th Century Fraktur Scripts using Open Source Engines (Version 1). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1810.03436>.

⁹ Ehrmann, M., Romanello, M., Najem-Meyer, S., Doucet, A., & Clematide, S. (2022). Extended Overview of HIPE-2022: Named Entity Recognition and Linking in Multilingual Historical Documents. In G. Faggioli, N. Ferro, A. Hanbury, & M. Potthast (Hrsg.), *Proceedings of the Working Notes of CLEF 2022—Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum* (Bd. 3180). <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3180/paper-83.pdf>.

¹⁰ Kasprzik, A. (2023). Aufbau eines produktiven Dienstes für die automatisierte Inhaltserschließung an der ZBW. o-bib. Das offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB, pp. 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.5282/O-BIB/5903>. Suominen, O. (2019). Annif: DIY automated subject indexing using multiple algorithms. *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries*, 29(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10285>.

¹¹ Paullada, A., Raji, I. D., Bender, E. M., Denton, E., & Hanna, A. (2021). Data and its (dis)contents: A survey of dataset development and use in machine learning research. *Patterns*, 2(11), 100336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100336>.

¹² Finetuning bezeichnet den Prozess der Anpassung eines *machine learning*-Modells an eine bestimmte Aufgabe oder seine Verbesserung durch ein Training mit zusätzlichen Daten.

¹³ Cordell, R. (2020). *Machine Learning + Libraries*. <https://labs.loc.gov/static/labs/work/reports/Cordell-LOC-ML-report.pdf?loclr=blsig>.

guide is also intended to provide support in this regard. More narrowly, the challenge is to create domain-specific ground truth or training datasets. In addition, it should be borne in mind that the transformative effects of machine learning projects require new types of analysis objects and thus a rethinking, and therefore confront cultural heritage practitioners, archivists and information scientists alike with the question of how the new data objects created for or by machine learning are to be documented and how these new objects can be related to the source materials. Computer vision datasets are a good example for this: Many of the data in cultural heritage institutions are available in the form of image files, which does not mean that these datasets are immediately suitable for the development of computer vision applications. With regard to the publication and use of datasets, there is a lack of standards in the cultural heritage sector; in view of the heterogeneity of these datasets, it is also unlikely that there will ever be a single standard that applies to all areas. As will be explained below, the aim here is to create transparency with regard to data publications and to provide a comprehensive documentation in the form of a datasheet.

Another challenge is that most currently developed industrial machine learning applications have been trained on contemporary datasets. While the cultural heritage sector has a large treasure trove of public domain sources, digitised materials from the 20th and 21st centuries pose particular challenges in terms of copyright, which are not easy to resolve. For this reason, cultural heritage institutions have so far mainly digitised historical materials that are from a legal perspective unproblematic and for which industrial machine learning applications are not suitable. Processes for providing objects that are still rights-protected are in the context of machine learning still in their infancy. As part of a project funded by the German Research Foundation DFG,¹⁴ possibilities in the application of standardised rights information for the description of legally protected digital objects are currently being identified and gaps closed using sample collections. Particular attention is being paid to the application of the Library Rights Machine-readable Language (LibRML) in order to describe access or usage restrictions in a machine-readable form. Another alternative are systems providing compute-to-data, which enable protected spaces with granular access for text and data mining on licensed objects.¹⁵ Scarcity of resources is, of course, one of the biggest practical barriers to the provision of cultural heritage datasets, as it requires that existing expertise can drive the creation of such datasets. Finally, the gap between research and cultural heritage institutions presents the latter with the challenge that staff should fundamentally understand the machine learning workflow¹⁶ in order to guide a collection through the various processing steps from digitisation to the creation of a dataset and its publication. In conclusion, it should be noted that research data will be integrated into the catalogue systems and infrastructures of cultural heritage institutions in the foreseeable future: Datasets suitable for machine learning will become part of digitisation workflows and help structure key discovery and research experiences. Currently, however, such datasets are rarely included or integrated into the interfaces through which most users and researchers come into contact with Collections as Data, so that the contributions of cultural heritage institutions to machine learning research remain more theoretical than practical due to a lack of discoverability. Against this background, the need to present recommendations and practical examples

¹⁴ <https://schutzrechte.hypothesen.org/>.

¹⁵ <https://blog.crossasia.org/vom-lesenden-menschen-zu-lernenden-maschinen-ueber-die-moeglichkeiten-von-gaia-x-fuer-das-kulturelle-erbe/>.

¹⁶ Mueller, J. P., & Mueller, L. (2016). *Machine Learning for Dummies*. <http://archive.org/details/machine-learning-for-dummies>; Ng, A. (2018). *Machine Learning Yearning. Technical Strategy for AI Engineers, In the Era of Deep Learning*. deeplearning.ai. <https://info.deeplearning.ai/machine-learning-yearning-book>.

to support GLAM institutions in making cultural heritage datasets available for use in machine learning research becomes evident.

A Checklist for the Publication of Cultural Heritage Data

Ideally, the creation and evaluation of a machine-readable cultural heritage dataset follows a systematic process with the steps (a) identification or selection of suitable data, (b) access and retrieval of the data, (c) data cleaning and, if necessary, reformatting (from specific standards such as MARC, Dublin Core, METS and TEI into formats such as CSV, JSON and RDF), (d) enrichment or annotation of the data, (e) package the dataset (adding metadata, licence information and documentation), and (f) analysis and publication on suitable platforms. This process can well be structured with a checklist.¹⁷ Such a checklist helps cultural heritage institutions to avoid common mistakes and to follow best practices, thus contributing to a standardisation that facilitates the re-use of similarly structured datasets. The main challenges in creating Collections as Data are data preparation and structuring of the datasets as well as issues of licensing and restrictions on use. In the cultural heritage sector, problems with data quality typically arise when using automated processes for digitisation and data preparation, especially if standard procedures such as optical character recognition (OCR) or named entity recognition / disambiguation / linking (NER/EL) are applied. In addition, problems often arise due to incoherent data and inconsistencies, e.g. in the descriptive metadata. The use of ontologies, controlled vocabularies and identifiers is common in the cultural heritage sector, but it can lead to its own difficulties (multilingualism / translatability of linked open data, persistence vs. versioning of identifiers, etc.). Information on standards and best practices in terms of file formats, metadata, data structure and the assessment and (post-selection) normalisation of available data can be seen as frequently requested information with regard to data preparation. Given the wide range of possibilities for producing datasets of different types for different usage scenarios, it is recommended to refer to documented examples of already published cultural heritage datasets (see the sections Examples of Datasets and Datasheets below).

Candela et al. (2023) present the following checklist for cultural heritage institutions, where no specific order applies here.¹⁸ This checklist is complemented by an interactive workflow that can be accessed online.¹⁹

1. specify a permissive licence that allows unrestricted re-use of the dataset (e.g. CC0, CC BY, see section 'Licences')
2. submit a proposal on how the dataset can be cited (see section 'Citation Information')
3. attach documentation to the dataset (see section 'Documentation')

¹⁷ Comp. Candela, G., Sáez, M. D., Escobar Esteban, Mp., & Marco-Such, M. (2022). Reusing digital collections from GLAM institutions. *Journal of Information Science*, 48(2), 251–267. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520950246>.

¹⁸ Candela, G., Gabriëls, N., Chambers, S., Dobрева, M., Ames, S., Ferriter, M., Fitzgerald, N., Harbo, V., Hofmann, K., Holownia, O., Irollo, A., Mahey, M., Manchester, E., Pham, T.-A., Potter, A., & Van Keer, E. (2023). A checklist to publish collections as data in GLAM institutions. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2023-0195>; Lee, B. C. G. (2023). The "Collections as ML Data" Checklist for Machine Learning & Cultural Heritage. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24765>, p. 7.

¹⁹ Candela, G., Chambers, S., & Irollo, A. (2024, Januar 12). *A workflow to publish Collections as Data: The case of Cultural Heritage data spaces*. Version 1. <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/I3jvP6>.

4. use a publicly accessible platform for the publication of the dataset (see section 'Platforms and Repositories')
5. provide additional examples of use in the documentation (see section 'Documentation')
6. structure the dataset (see section 'Dataset Structure')
7. provide machine-readable metadata about the dataset itself (see section 'Machine-readable Metadata')
8. integrate your dataset into collaborative annotation platforms (see section 'Collaborative Annotation Platforms')
9. offer an API for accessing your repository (see section 'Application Programming Interfaces')
10. develop a portal page on which the dataset is presented (see section 'Portals')
11. add terms of use (see section 'Terms of use')

In the following text, explanations of the individual points of this checklist will be presented. In addition, recommendations on curation and quality assurance as well as numerous examples will be added.

Licences

The majority of digitisation projects in the Federal Republic of Germany are financed by public funds. As a general rule, the funding bodies stipulate that datasets must be published under permissive licences. Unlike copyright law, licences define the conditions under which content can be used in a legally secure manner without any further individual agreement.²⁰ Permissive licences²¹ are licences such as CC0²² or Public Domain Mark 1.0²³ that do not contain any conditions for use, which in turn allow the resulting products to be freely licensed and therefore also permit commercial or non-free subsequent use. The modular Creative Commons licences have developed into an internationally accepted standard for free licences (for example: CC BY Attribution, CC BY-SA Share Alike, CC BY-NC Non Commercial, CC BY-ND No Derivatives, CC0).²⁴ However, only CC BY, CC BY-SA and CC0 are considered permissive licences in the narrower sense. Cultural heritage institutions can choose from these licences depending on the requirements of the third-party funder. The works presented in the digitised collections of the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin – Preußischer Kulturbesitz (Berlin State Library – Prussian Cultural Heritage) are subject to a public domain licence by default, while the metadata are released under CC0. The datasets published by the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin on Zenodo are mostly released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)²⁵ licence,²⁶ as their curation implies a threshold of originality.

Alternatives to the frequently used Creative Commons licences include the "Datenlizenz Deutschland 2.0",²⁷ which is available in the variants 'Attribution' and 'Zero'. This licence is used for public data from government bodies and institutions in Germany. The disadvantage of this licence, however, is that it is

²⁰ Klimpel, P. (2022). *Kulturelles Erbe digital – eine kleine Rechtsfibel*. <https://doi.org/10.12752/2.0.004.0>.

²¹ This term designates licenses with minimal restrictions for the use, adjustment or dissemination of data.

²² <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.de>.

²³ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/deed.de>.

²⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>.

²⁵ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode.de>.

²⁶ Comp. <https://zenodo.org/communities/stabi/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>.

²⁷ <https://www.govdata.de/web/guest/lizenzen>.

tailored only to the German legal system. RightsStatements.org was created by a consortium of cultural heritage institutions, including Europeana and the Digital Public Library of America, to meet the need for standardised and interoperable tools for communicating the copyright and reuse status of digital objects. The Rightsstatements.org portal²⁸ offers twelve standardised licences, including for objects and data for which third-party rights exist or for which no rights of use can be granted or Creative Commons licences can be used.

The use of permissive licences in the cultural heritage sector is currently the subject of heated debate.²⁹ The background to this is the fact that freely available datasets are being used in AI research, particularly by international big tech companies, to create AI applications with the aim of integrating or utilising them in commercial products. Freely available datasets are intended to stimulate innovation and research and encourage the creation of new cultural works; commercial re-utilisation is certainly desirable under certain conditions, particularly with a view to strengthening the national and European creative industries. In view of the economic power of big tech companies, however, it is questionable whether publicly funded data should continue to strengthen such corporations. For this reason, one side of the current debate is in favour of covering the costs of providing curated datasets via licence fees for commercial purposes and therefore charging for the cost-intensive quality assurance and maintenance of the data.³⁰ The other side, by contrast, maintains the position that tax-funded data should always be made available as freely as possible under permissive licences.³¹

Citation Information

The publication of a dataset should be accompanied by a citation proposal, for example in BibTeX and APA format. It is important to include a persistent identifier (such as a DOI, a PURL, an URN or a handle) into the proposal so that the dataset can be clearly identified.

Documentation: Datasheets for Datasets, Model Cards for Model Reporting

In addition to the compilation and curation of datasets, a datasheet should always be attached to a data publication, for example in the case of bulk downloads. The impetus for this came from a number of researchers³² with the intention of standardising the process for documenting datasets. In principle, it is

²⁸ <https://rightsstatements.org/de/>.

²⁹ Comp. here the positions of the KB – National Library of the Netherlands (<https://www.kb.nl/en/nieuws/kb-restricts-access-to-collections-for-training-commercial-ai>) and of Europeana (<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/ai-opt-outs-should-cultural-heritage-institutions-dis-allow-the-mining-of-cultural-heritage-data>).

³⁰ The European Union's Data Governance Act, which applies starting from September 24, 2023, contains a tool relevant to the debate, namely the chapter on the use of data by public sector bodies (Chapter II, Article 6), which regulates the provision of data for a fee. It states that public sector bodies may differentiate between private users or small and medium-sized enterprises on the one hand and larger companies, which no longer fall under the former definition, on the other. This creates an opportunity for differentiation among commercial users, with the fees being based on the costs of the provision infrastructure. Comp. also <https://mmk.sbb.berlin/2023/03/24/on-the-use-of-licences-in-times-of-large-language-models/?lang=en>.

³¹ Comp. here, for example, Klimpel, 2022, *ibidem*.

³² Gebru, T., Morgenstern, J., Vecchione, B., Vaughan, J. W., Wallach, H., Daumé III, H., & Crawford, K. (2021). Datasheets for Datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(12), 86–92.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3458723>; Heger, A. K., Marquis, L. B., Vorvoreanu, M., Wallach, H., & Wortman

unlikely that a machine learning model will work well if it is used in a context that does not match its training and test datasets. In addition, the risk of datasets containing undesirable distortions ('biases' or statistical or content-related skews) should be countered. To counter this, the creation of "datasheets for datasets" was proposed to accompany the publication of data. Similar to instruction leaflets, these datasheets provide the context required for the further use of datasets; they create space for negotiations and facilitate interdisciplinary cooperation. Datasheets document the motivation for creating the datasets, their composition, the creation process and the recommended uses, and they enable transparency, fairness and accountability in the handling of the data. This supports developers in the machine learning sector, researchers and cultural heritage practitioners in selecting suitable datasets and promotes further developments based on digitised cultural heritage in the field of AI. Finally, such documentation will promote the reproducibility of machine learning models and results in the field of AI research.

However, it should be borne in mind that cultural heritage datasets differ significantly from industrial datasets currently used in AI: Cultural heritage datasets are heterogeneous in terms of the time period covered, the location or regions included in them, or the cultural contexts in which they need to be categorised. Most cultural heritage datasets grow over time as recently digitised objects are added in incremental steps, whereas industrial datasets are often self-contained compilations that have only been published once. Exceptions to this rule include Common Crawl³³ and Wikipedia, whose datasets are created iteratively or grow continuously. The importance of usage rights and provenance as well as the use of linked open data (LOD, e.g. RDF) are characteristic features of cultural heritage datasets. Their intended use is often research, in contrast to the commercial use of contemporary datasets. The selection of the data and the curation of the metadata were carried out by specially trained cultural heritage professionals. This high quality of data from the cultural heritage sector stands in stark contrast to the annotation of contemporary data, which is often carried out by underpaid workers.³⁴

To date, several templates for datasheets have already been developed; they are mostly modular in structure and are formed by lists of questions to be considered in each case. In order to do justice to the specifics of cultural heritage datasets, separate datasheets have been developed for this field,³⁵ in which specific questions are to be answered. In principle, it is up to each cultural heritage institution to decide how the datasheet is designed in detail. The literature listed is for guidance only. However, it is always

Vaughan, J. (2022). Understanding Machine Learning Practitioners' Data Documentation Perceptions, Needs, Challenges, and Desiderata. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(CSCW2), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3555760>; Jo, E. S., & Gebru, T. (2020). Lessons from archives: Strategies for collecting sociocultural data in machine learning. *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 306–316. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372829>; Pushkarna, M., Zaldivar, A., & Kjartansson, O. (2022). Data Cards: Purposeful and Transparent Dataset Documentation for Responsible AI. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 1776–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533231>.

³³ <https://commoncrawl.org/>.

³⁴ Miceli, M., Posada, J., & Yang, T. (2022). Studying Up Machine Learning Data: Why Talk About Bias When We Mean Power? *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(GROUP), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3492853>.

³⁵ Alkemade, H., Claeysens, S., Colavizza, G., Freire, N., Lehmann, J., Neudecker, C., Osti, G., & Van Strien, D. (2023). Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9, 17. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>; comp. also Lee, 2023, ibidem.

advisable to provide information on the motivation for creating the dataset, its dissemination along with possible contact persons, its composition, the selection process, any annotations added, the intended use, ethical considerations and the future maintenance of the dataset. Ideally, these datasheets should result out of an interdisciplinary dialogue between domain experts (librarians, archivists and other practitioners in the field of cultural heritage) and researchers and technicians (developers, information scientists, IT experts). Such an approach not only emphasises the function of datasheets as “boundary objects”³⁶ or as a vehicle for interdisciplinary collaboration, thus ensuring a high degree of interpretative flexibility, but also serves to create transparency. Remarkably, one of the key publications on this topic states: „[...] the shared dominant perception was that transparency artifacts were ironically opaque. The opacity in documentation, quite simply, increases when language used is technical, dense, and presumptive of a reader’s background, making it difficult for non-technical stakeholders to interpret. [...] transparency is attained when we establish a shared and socratic understanding of datasets based on the ability to ask and answer questions over time”.³⁷ In addition, the datasheets should be written in English, as this is the language spoken by the entire machine learning community.

If a cultural heritage institution by itself trains machine learning models, it is advisable to create model cards for the respective model in the same vein as datasheets. The relevant scientific reference for this is the publication “Model Cards for Model Reporting”.³⁸ The Hugging Face Hub provides a good example of what such a model card could look like;³⁹ it offers a solid template for such model cards, i.e. a template with supporting questions and recommendations. There is also a tool on Hugging Face that offers the option of downloading the completed model card in Markdown format after filling in the relevant fields and then converting it into other formats if necessary.⁴⁰

Platforms and Repositories

Data are not just electronic objects, they also have a social life. Platforms and repositories are therefore only partly data silos; they often also become places where (research) communities meet and exchange ideas. In principle, the choice of one or more repositories on which a dataset is published should therefore be based on the target group that is to be reached with the publication. Repositories that are reliably used by the relevant user communities increase the visibility of such datasets. Publicly accessible repositories are therefore a recommended addition to the platforms provided by cultural heritage institutions. They may be more suitable for the publication of large datasets, they may not incur operating costs for the cultural heritage institution, or the latter may not have a publicly accessible platform itself. The decision as to where a dataset should be published is left to each cultural heritage institution; it is entirely possible and also sensible to publish a dataset in parallel in different repositories in order to reach a wide audience and thus ensure maximum impact with regard to the use of a dataset

³⁶ Star, S. L., & Griesemer, J. R. (1989). Institutional Ecology, ‘Translations’ and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley’s Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907–39. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631289019003001>.

³⁷ Pushkarna et al., 2022, *ibidem* p. 1779.

³⁸ Mitchell, M., Wu, S., Zaldivar, A., Barnes, P., Vasserman, L., Hutchinson, B., Spitzer, E., Raji, I. D., & Gebru, T. (2019). Model Cards for Model Reporting. *Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287596>.

³⁹ https://huggingface.co/docs/huggingface_hub/how-to-model-cards.

⁴⁰ https://huggingface.co/spaces/huggingface/Model_Cards_Writing_Tool.

in different contexts. In addition, datasets published in different locations remain available at all times, because the 'LOCKS' principle applies: 'lots of copies keep stuff safe'.

The two largest and most common international platforms and repositories for the publication of datasets are Zenodo and the Hugging Face Hub, with the latter already specifically targeting the machine learning community. Other repositories that are widespread in Europe, albeit less well-known, are those of the DARIAH infrastructure (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), such as the DARIAH-DE Repository,⁴¹ which enables the long-term digital archiving of research data in the humanities and cultural sciences, Europeana,⁴² the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage⁴³ and the European Data Space for Cultural Heritage,⁴⁴ which is to be established in the coming years. At a national level, the German Digital Library DDB⁴⁵ and the national research data infrastructures (NFDIs, e.g. NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Memory) are relevant, in which datasets located in repositories and data portals operated by the institutions themselves should also be catalogued and thus made visible.⁴⁶

Zenodo⁴⁷ is an internationally recognised repository for research datasets, which is operated by CERN and funded by the European Commission. Data records up to 50 GB in size can be archived permanently and free of charge on Zenodo. If a cultural heritage institution sets up a so-called 'community' account, which is also free of charge, the storage space is not limited. Publishing datasets on Zenodo is very simple, and documentation provides support.⁴⁸ The data publications receive a citable DOI (digital object identifier), which can also be reserved in advance and inserted into accompanying publications like datasheets for datasets. Zenodo offers the option of choosing from a whole range of standard licences. The versioning of datasets – for example in the event of their modification or extension – is also supported by default. Data can also be uploaded via the Zenodo REST API.⁴⁹

The US-American company Hugging Face operates the Hugging Face Hub⁵⁰ and, as part of this, a library of datasets.⁵¹ In contrast to Zenodo, the service is aimed specifically at the machine learning community and therefore offers the major advantage that datasets published there can be linked to the models trained on them. As users are also offered computing capacities, the Hugging Face Hub offers a complete ecosystem and therefore an ideal working environment for developers. The relevant community involved in AI research is therefore most likely to be reached here. It also has the capacity to store large datasets and the models trained on them. The Hugging Face Hub enables the upload of datasets and models with Git and Git-LFS,⁵² whereby the upload of even very large datasets can be

⁴¹ <https://de.dariah.eu/repository>.

⁴² <https://www.europeana.eu/>.

⁴³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en.

⁴⁴ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/common-european-data-space-for-cultural-heritage>.

⁴⁵ <https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/>.

⁴⁶ <https://nfdi4culture.de/> bzw. <https://www.nfdi4objects.net/>.

⁴⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>.

⁴⁸ <https://help.zenodo.org/>.

⁴⁹ <https://developers.zenodo.org/#rest-api>.

⁵⁰ <https://huggingface.co/>.

⁵¹ <https://huggingface.co/datasets>.

⁵² <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/repositories-getting-started>.

automated so that no additional work is required. Although the service is aimed at the machine learning community in general, cultural heritage institutions are involved in this repository through the BigLAM initiative.⁵³ This supports the strategic interest of this user group with the aim of improving the findability of datasets and making machine learning applications available. The Hugging Face Hub also makes it possible to upload different versions of models and datasets. Old versions of the same model or dataset can still be retrieved after an update has been published, thanks to the Git-based version management system. However, it becomes more complex for the providing organisations if datasets are also published together with the models – these datasets should also be kept up to date and new commits should also be made for the datasets if they have been changed. However, Hugging Face does not provide any information on long-term storage. Another disadvantage compared to Zenodo is that the Hugging Face Hub does offer the option of adding DOIs after to the publication of models and datasets, but these DOIs must be added manually after the upload⁵⁴ and it is not (yet) possible to reserve a DOI as is the case with Zenodo.⁵⁵ Finally, the Hugging Face Hub is described as a ‘community and data science platform’; nevertheless, Hugging Face is financed by venture capital, which raises the fundamental question of sustainability. Hugging Face’s documentation is self-referential⁵⁶ and says nothing about the company’s mission and vision, goals or possible future monetisation of the hub. This background information opposes choosing the Hugging Face Hub as the sole publication venue; rather, datasets and models should be published on more than one platform in order to guarantee the possibility of long-term storage and permanently free availability in the sense of open access.

In addition to the platforms and repositories already mentioned, there are a number of other research-relevant data portals whose offerings are dedicated to specific tasks and are therefore aimed at specific research communities. The European Language Resources Association Catalogue ELRA,⁵⁷ the European Language Grid (ELG)⁵⁸ and the repositories of the CLARIN infrastructure (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)⁵⁹ are available for the publication of language resources and the development of applications in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). At national level, the Text+⁶⁰ consortium is responsible for this as part of the NFDI. The International Association for Pattern Recognition (IAPR), in this case the Technical Committee 11,⁶¹ offers a repository for the field of computer vision and in particular for document image analysis and recognition – a common area of work for libraries. For the recognition of handwritten texts, there is a community-driven repository on GitHub⁶² that provides training datasets for the creation of transcription or segmentation models. This provides a public alternative to Transkribus,⁶³ probably the best-known portal in this area, which is now subject to a fee.

⁵³ <https://huggingface.co/biglam>.

⁵⁴ <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/doi>.

⁵⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hugging_Face.

⁵⁶ <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/index>.

⁵⁷ <http://catalogue.elra.info/en-us/>.

⁵⁸ <https://live.european-language-grid.eu/>.

⁵⁹ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/data>.

⁶⁰ <https://text-plus.org/>.

⁶¹ <https://tc11.cvc.uab.es/>.

⁶² <https://htr-united.github.io/document-your-data.html>.

⁶³ <https://readcoop.eu/transkribus/>.

Dataset Structure

Digital content can be available in a whole range of different media types, such as text, images, metadata, audio recordings or video. The structure of cultural heritage datasets therefore varies according to size and content type. There are various options that enable researchers and users to quickly grasp this structure. These include self-explanatory folder names ('text', 'images'; or 'images', 'labels'), the use of unambiguous and descriptive file names and formats ('filename.txt', 'filename.xml') or the use of an identifier in the file name. If different file formats are used for each resource (such as JPEG, TIFF, XML, JSON), a base folder can be created for each of these formats. Another option is to structure the content using the metadata of the dataset and provide the dataset in a series of files in different formats (e.g., in Dublin Core as well as in MARC). Users can then decide for themselves which format they prefer.

Machine-Readable Metadata

Making metadata available for digital resources is one of the core tasks of cultural heritage institutions. However, there are a variety of forms and formats that can be used here; the DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation document the various options.⁶⁴ The metadata and formats commonly used in the cultural heritage sector do not necessarily correspond to those used in the machine learning sector. This gap needs to be closed. The use of interoperable, machine-readable metadata is therefore necessary and improves the findability and utilisation of the cultural heritage datasets provided, as the metadata can be further processed without additional effort. Examples of standards and vocabularies that can be used to provide metadata are MARC,⁶⁵ Dublin Core,⁶⁶ the Resource Description Framework (RDF)⁶⁷ and schema.org.⁶⁸ Other examples are the Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)⁶⁹ and the Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VoID),⁷⁰ which are provided by the World Wide Web Consortium.

Collaborative Annotation Platforms

In the cultural heritage sector in particular, collaborative annotation and editing platforms have become an important tool for engaging users and enriching collections, for example through annotations and links to other resources. The term 'collaborative annotation platforms' primarily refers to existing infrastructures such as Hypothesis,⁷¹ Mirador⁷² or Wikidata,⁷³ which do not have their own collection presentations. The Swiss GLAM community, for example, has long been uploading its digital holdings to Wikimedia Commons, which in turn are catalogued with Wikidata;⁷⁴ a range of upload tools are available

⁶⁴ Altenhöner, R., Berger, A., Bracht, C., Klimpel, P., Meyer, S., Neuburger, A., Stäcker, T., & Stein, R. (2023). *DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation. Updaten version 2022*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561147>.

⁶⁵ <https://www.loc.gov/marc/>.

⁶⁶ <https://www.dublincore.org/>.

⁶⁷ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>.

⁶⁸ <https://schema.org/>.

⁶⁹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>.

⁷⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/void/>.

⁷¹ <https://web.hypothes.is/>.

⁷² <https://projectmirador.org/>.

⁷³ <https://www.wikidata.org/>.

⁷⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/>.

for this purpose.⁷⁵ The British Library provides a selection of Jupyter notebooks via Wikidata⁷⁶ in order to simplify access to its digital collections.

Application Programming Interfaces

APIs enable users and electronic systems to programmatically access and retrieve data. The provision of an API therefore significantly contributes to the re-use of datasets. Examples of common APIs in the cultural heritage sector are IIIF,⁷⁷ OAI-PMH,⁷⁸ SRU,⁷⁹ SPARQL⁸⁰ and unAPI.⁸¹ When using an API to publish digital content, additional specifics may need to be considered. For example, when using IIIF, each resource should contain a manifest.json that describes the content of that resource. APIs are also usually used to provide metadata in formats such as Dublin Core, MARC or METS/MODS.

Portals

If a cultural heritage institution maintains its own lab⁸² with an internet presence, this is the best place to refer to the published datasets. However, the use of a portal page – or more simply: a web page within the cultural heritage institution's website – also improves the visibility of the dataset and supports the provision of additional information that is helpful for the reuse of the datasets. Citation suggestions, the accompanying documentation of the dataset and terms of use can also be provided here.

Terms of Use

It is best practice to attach terms of use to a data publication that go beyond the licence and clearly outline the conditions for the use of this data. The EThOS dataset of the British Library, for example, contains a section with terms of use in which copyright, liability and access conditions are described.⁸³ Furthermore, as in the documentation, additional aspects can be described here, e.g. how inappropriate content or the violation of personal rights can be reported; the Royal Danish Library, for example, provides such terms of service for its entire Library Open Access Repository.⁸⁴

Curation and Quality Assessment

Depending on the type of media used, there are different quality criteria according to which cultural heritage datasets can be evaluated. In principle, these datasets should comply with the FAIR data principles, i.e. fulfil the principles of **f**indability, **a**ccessibility, **i**nteroperability and **r**eusability.⁸⁵ Specific

⁷⁵ <https://www.zhbluzern.ch/home/zentralgut-in-wikimedia-commons-2865>.

⁷⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q111421205>.

⁷⁷ <https://iiif.io/>.

⁷⁸ <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>.

⁷⁹ <http://www.loc.gov/standards/sru/sru-1-2.html>.

⁸⁰ <http://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>.

⁸¹ <https://wiki.k10plus.de/display/K10PLUS/UnAPI>.

⁸² Comp. here <https://glamlabs.io/list-members/>.

⁸³ <https://ethos.bl.uk/ViewTerms.do>.

⁸⁴ https://loar.kb.dk/assets/RDL/pdfs/LOAR_TermsofService_v3_KB.pdf.

⁸⁵ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., Da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>; Tóth-Czifra, E. (2020). 10. The Risk of Losing the Thick Description: Data Management Challenges Faced by the Arts and Humanities in the Evolving FAIR Data Ecosystem. In

quality criteria can then be created for the respective media types,⁸⁶ such as freedom from errors, completeness or interoperability for Linked Open Data datasets⁸⁷ or the use of controlled vocabularies, publications, Wikidata properties or Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records FRBR.⁸⁸ For text corpora, Candela et al.⁸⁹ have developed exemplary criteria that make it possible to assess the quality of a published (or to-be-published) dataset. The procedure developed in this article can also be transferred or adapted to other types of media. Accordingly, such datasets should contain information on licences, the degree of accuracy, provenance, the language(s) included (in the case of text corpora), a persistent identifier, prototypical use, the (machine-readable) formats in which the data is available, the terms of use and any code of conduct, as well as technical aspects such as the availability of APIs for retrieval. In the study by Candela et al.,⁹⁰ the datasets analysed there are given a value between 0 and 1 for each criterion mentioned. These values are transferred to a network diagram, which on the one hand enables a comparison of the quality of different datasets and on the other hand allows the identification of so-called 'benchmark' datasets, i.e. datasets that can serve as a benchmark due to their quality. To assess the quality of OCR results, which have an impact on downstream tasks such as text and data mining, the explanations by Neudecker et al. and van Strien et al. are helpful.⁹¹ In addition to text and image datasets, the publication of datasets containing only metadata is a typical task in cultural heritage institutions. If possible, metadata created according to the RDA (Resource Description and Access) framework should be made available. It uses standardised data links and controlled vocabularies. The resulting data are available in formats such as MARC21 or PICA-XML and are evaluated in the same way

J. Edmond (Hrsg.), *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research* (pp. 235–266). Open Book Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.11647/obp.0192.10>.

⁸⁶ Carrasco, R. C., Candela, G., & Marco-Such, M. (2025). Measuring the diversity of data and metadata in digital libraries. *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, 26(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-025-00411-1>.

⁸⁷ Candela, G., Escobar, P., Sáez, M. D., & Marco-Such, M. (2023). A Shape Expression approach for assessing the quality of Linked Open Data in libraries. *Semantic Web*, 14(2), 159–179. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-210441>.

⁸⁸ Candela, G., Escobar, P., Carrasco, R. C., & Marco-Such, M. (2022). Evaluating the quality of linked open data in digital libraries. *Journal of Information Science*, 48(1), 21–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520930951>.

⁸⁹ Candela, G., Sáez, M.-D., Escobar, P., & Marco-Such, M. (2021). A benchmark of Spanish language datasets for computationally driven research. *Journal of Information Science*, 016555152110605. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211060530>.

⁹⁰ Candela et al., 2021, *ibidem*.

⁹¹ Neudecker, C., Zaczynska, K., Baierer, K., Rehm, G., Gerber, M., & Schneider, J. M. (2021). Methoden und Metriken zur Messung von OCR-Qualität für die Kuratierung von Daten und Metadaten. In M. Franke-Maier, A. Kasprzik, A. Ledl, & H. Schürmann (Hrsg.), *Qualität in der Inhaltsschließung* (pp. 137–166). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110691597-009>; van Strien, D., Beelen, K., Ardanuy, M., Hosseini, K., McGillivray, B., & Colavizza, G. (2020). Assessing the Impact of OCR Quality on Downstream NLP Tasks. *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*, 484–496. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0009169004840496>.

as Linked Open Data.⁹² Software on GitHub⁹³ and quality assessment studies⁹⁴ are available for the evaluation of metadata according to older regulations.

Examples for Formats and Standards

Obviously, different file formats are more or less suitable for different tasks (e.g. the publication of ground truth data). Some of the most common formats are briefly presented below, whereby the different formats are often recommended for different types of data, for example XML data such as TEI, PAGE-XML, ALTO for text data, TIFF, JPEG/JPEG2000 and PNG for image data as well as databases or row/column-based formats such as CSV, TSV, IOB or Arrow for metadata.

- TEI: This refers to an XML standard for digital texts that has been developed by the Text Encoding Initiative since the early 1980s. The XML format is set out in the TEI guidelines and is semantic rather than presentation-based, with the guidelines defining the semantics and interpretation of each tag and attribute. The TEI standard is used in editorial science, linguistics and generally in the (digital) humanities for encoding and exchanging texts. However, one disadvantage of TEI is its high degree of flexibility, which to some extent prevents interoperability even between different data written in TEI. Here it is advisable to use an established standard set of elements, such as the basic format defined by the German Text Archive DTA.⁹⁵
- PAGE-XML: This XML standard, which is specifically designed for the evaluation of pattern recognition processes such as optical character recognition (OCR), handwritten text recognition (HTR) and machine learning, was developed by the Pattern Recognition & Image Analysis Lab (PRIMA)⁹⁶ at the University of Salford in Manchester. PAGE can be resolved to **P**age **A**nalysis and **G**round Truth **E**lements, as it contains information about the organisation and structure of a page as well as its content. Results of the layout analysis, regions, lines, reading order, ground truth etc. can be stored in PAGE-XML format. The OCR-D project has published detailed transcription guidelines for historical documents.⁹⁷ Examples for ground truth files in this area are the IMPACT dataset of historical

⁹² Comp. here also Candela, G., Escobar, P., Carrasco, R. C., & Marco-Such, M. (2022). Evaluating the quality of linked open data in digital libraries. *Journal of Information Science*, 48(1), 21–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520930951>.

⁹³ <https://github.com/pkiralay/qa-catalogue>.

⁹⁴ Király, P. (2019). Validating 126 million MARC records. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Digital Access to Textual Cultural Heritage*, 161–168. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3322905.3322929>; Ungváry, R., & Király, P. (2021). Bemerkungen zu der Qualitätsbewertung von MARC-21-Datensätzen. In M. Franke-Maier, A. Kasprzik, A. Ledl, & H. Schürmann (Hrsg.), *Qualität in der Inhaberschliefung* (pp. 177–228). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110691597-011>.

⁹⁵ <https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/doku/basisformat/>.

⁹⁶ <https://www.primaresearch.org/>.

⁹⁷ <https://ocr-d.de/en/gt-guidelines/trans/>.

document images,⁹⁸ the Europeana Newspapers Project (ENP) image and ground truth dataset of historical newspapers⁹⁹ or the OCR-D Ground Truth dataset.¹⁰⁰

- ALTO: ALTO is also an XML schema that is often used in combination with the Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard METS to describe an entire digitised object. The abbreviation ALTO stands for **A**nalyzed **L**ayout and **T**ext **O**bject and made it possible for the first time to link full texts created via OCR with the pixel coordinates of the digital facsimile, for example to highlight search results in colour in presentation platforms for digital collections. ALTO has established itself as the standard format for full texts in the library sector through its inclusion in the standard catalogue of the Library of Congress and is maintained and continuously developed by an international editorial board.
- Row and column-based formats (CSV, TSV): TSV format (**t**ab-**s**eparated **v**alues, 'filename.tsv'), e.g. for named entity recognition / entity linking. This is a table format in which the columns are separated from each other by a tab and there is a token in each row; other columns are used for the annotations. The TSV format was used for the GermEval 2014 NER Shared Task,¹⁰¹ for example. The CoNLL-U format, in which syntactic and morphological annotations are stored, is also a tab-delimited format.¹⁰² INCEpTION, which supports the export of TSV files,¹⁰³ can be mentioned as an annotation tool. The CSV format is structured analogue to the TSV format (**c**omma-**s**eparated **v**alues, 'filename.csv'); a comma is used internationally as a separator, in the European context it is usually a semicolon.
- IOB format (**I**nside, **O**utside, **B**eginning, 'filename.bio'). This standard was developed back in the 1990s to be able to add annotations to tokens.¹⁰⁴ It was used for the CoNLL-2000 Shared Task,¹⁰⁵ for example, or for the CLEF 2020 HIPE Shared Task.¹⁰⁶ This format can, e.g., be exported from INCEpTION, the successor project to WebAnno.¹⁰⁷

⁹⁸ Papadopoulos, C., Pletschacher, S., Clausner, C., & Antonacopoulos, A. (2013). The IMPACT dataset of historical document images. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Historical Document Imaging and Processing*, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2501115.2501130>.

⁹⁹ Clausner, C., Papadopoulos, C., Pletschacher, S., & Antonacopoulos, A. (2015). The ENP image and ground truth dataset of historical newspapers. *2015 13th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR)*, 931–935. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2015.7333898>.

¹⁰⁰ Boenig, M., Baierer, K., Hartmann, V., Federbusch, M., & Neudecker, C. (2019). Labelling OCR Ground Truth for Usage in Repositories. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Digital Access to Textual Cultural Heritage*, 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3322905.3322916>.

¹⁰¹ <https://sites.google.com/site/germeval2014ner/data>. See also Benikova, D., Biemann, C., & Reznicek, M. (2014). NoSta-D Named Entity Annotation for German: Guidelines and Dataset. *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'14)*, 2524–2531. http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2014/pdf/276_Paper.pdf.

¹⁰² <https://universaldependencies.org/format.html>.

¹⁰³ <https://inception-project.github.io/>.

¹⁰⁴ Ramshaw, L. A., & Marcus, M. P. (1995). Text Chunking Using Transformation-Based Learning. In S. Armstrong, K. Church, P. Isabelle, S. Manzi, E. Tzoukermann, & D. Yarowsky (Hrsg.), *Natural Language Processing Using Very Large Corpora* (Bd. 11, pp. 157–176). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-2390-9_10.

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.cnts.ua.ac.be/conll2000/chunking/>.

¹⁰⁶ Ehrmann, M., Romanello, M., Bircher, S., & Clematide, S. (2020). Introducing the CLEF 2020 HIPE Shared Task: Named Entity Recognition and Linking on Historical Newspapers. In J. M. Jose, E. Yilmaz, J. Magalhães, P. Castells, N. Ferro, M. J. Silva, & F. Martins (Hrsg.), *Advances in Information Retrieval* (Bd. 12036, pp. 524–532). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-45442-5_68.

¹⁰⁷ <https://inception-project.github.io/>; see also <https://webanno.github.io/webanno/>.

- Image files (e.g. for layout recognition, OCR or image similarity searches) are usually saved in common formats such as TIFF, JPG or JPEG2000 or PNG, with additional information or annotations added as metadata. It is particularly important to choose image formats without or with lossless compression, as image processing methods are constantly evolving and can benefit from individual pixels that contain information. Examples of image datasets that are specifically annotated for computer vision tasks are the CIFAR-10 dataset¹⁰⁸ or the Newspaper Navigator dataset.¹⁰⁹ Tools for creating annotated image datasets include Annotorious,¹¹⁰ MakeSense.ai,¹¹¹ Labelme¹¹² or Label Studio.¹¹³
- Relational databases: If relational data is to be stored, this is possible in a relational database, for example. The database structure must be modelled according to strict specifications (Backus-Naur form or normal forms), and the various tables are related using a key¹¹⁴ (for example, the PPN – Pica Production Number – of a work).¹¹⁵ The advantage of relational databases is the speed of queries thanks to the strict formatting specifications. Frequently used relational databases are PostgreSQL, MySQL or SQLite. SQLite has the advantage of encapsulating the database in a single file, which in turn makes it particularly suitable for the transfer of data records. In its Recommended Formats Statement (RFS), the Library of Congress lists SQLite as the open and platform-independent and therefore preferred database system for relational datasets.¹¹⁶
- NoSQL databases: NoSQL databases such as MongoDB, CouchDB or Redis do without a relational structure of the data and instead have a flat structure, but are considerably slower when querying large amounts of data. They can efficiently store and manage unstructured or semi-structured data such as images, videos, texts, and metadata associated with artefacts. One of the key benefits is the ability to horizontally scale by adding more commodity hardware, making it cost-effective for growing collections. NoSQL's schema-less design allows institutions to adapt quickly to changing requirements and easily integrate new data sources without rigid schema constraints. Additionally, their high availability and fault tolerance ensure that valuable cultural data remains accessible, even in the event of hardware failures.
- Graph databases: Graph databases¹¹⁷ like the Resource Description Framework RDF,¹¹⁸ Neo4j¹¹⁹ or WikiBase¹²⁰ enable to model data as interconnected nodes and relationships. This structure is particularly well suited for representing complex cultural datasets, such as provenance, exhibitions, and artistic collaborations. Its strengths include the ability to uncover hidden connections and perform sophisticated queries across disparate collections.¹²¹ Graph databases also facilitate linked

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html>.

¹⁰⁹ <https://labs.loc.gov/work/experiments/newspaper-navigator/>.

¹¹⁰ <https://github.com/annotorious/annotorious>.

¹¹¹ <https://www.makesense.ai/>.

¹¹² <https://github.com/wkentaro/labelme>.

¹¹³ <https://labelstud.io/>.

¹¹⁴ [https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Schl%C3%BCssel_\(Datenbank\)](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Schl%C3%BCssel_(Datenbank)).

¹¹⁵ Datensatzidentifizier in großen Bibliotheksverbundkatalogen, z.B. dem K10+.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/RFS%202024-2025.pdf>.

¹¹⁷ <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Graphdatenbank>.

¹¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>.

¹¹⁹ <https://neo4j.com/>.

¹²⁰ <https://wikiba.se/>.

¹²¹ See e.g. the cooperative platform Culturegraph provided by the German National Library, which enables the networking of library collections. <https://hub.culturegraph.org/search>.

open data initiatives and enable institutions to contribute to a global network of interconnected cultural information. However, graph databases can be more complex to design and to query as compared to relational or NoSQL databases.

- Arrow format: The Arrow format is a special format that allows large amounts of data to be processed and moved quickly. It stores the data in a columnar storage layout. This offers a number of advantages. Arrow is column-oriented and therefore faster when querying and processing slices or columns of data; it supports many, possibly nested, column types, enables parallelised processing of large datasets and copy-free transfer to standard machine learning tools such as NumPy, Pandas, PyTorch and TensorFlow. The HuggingFace Datasets library¹²² uses the Arrow format for its local caching system. The architecture enables the use of large datasets on computers with relatively small device memory; this means that even very large datasets can be loaded quickly.

Examples for Datasets in Cultural Heritage

Organisation	Dataset	Description	Licence
Library of Congress	https://data.labs.loc.gov/packages/	Several pre-packaged datasets	Several licences
MoMA Collection Dataset	https://github.com/MuseumofModernArt/collection	Datasets of artworks and artists	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication
National Archives' Digital Public Library of America	https://dp.la/	Pre-packaged Primary Source Sets	Several licences
British Library	http://britishlibrary.github.io/dاتا.bl.uk/datasets/	Several pre-packaged datasets	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication
British Museum	https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/	Digital Asset Database	Several licences
Bibliothèque nationale de France	https://data.bnf.fr/	Main catalogue as linked open data (LOD)	Licence Ouverte de l'État
German Federal Archives	https://open-data.bundesarchiv.de/	Indexing data in EAD-XML format	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication
Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, Stabi Lab	https://lab.sbb.berlin/daten/	Several datasets	(mostly) Public Domain Mark
Biblioteca Nacional de España	https://datos.bne.es/inicio.html	Bibliographic data as LOD	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication
Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes	https://data.cervantesvirtual.com/datos-enlazados	Main catalogue as linked open data (LOD)	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

¹²² <https://huggingface.co/docs/datasets/index>.

National Library of Scotland's Data Foundry	https://data.nls.uk/data/	Several pre-packaged datasets	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication
Royal Danish Library KB Labs	https://labs.kb.dk/	Several pre-packaged datasets	Several licences
National Library of Luxemburg	https://data.bnl.lu/data/historical-newspapers/	Historical newspapers	CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

Examples for Datasheets in Cultural Heritage

Datasets from the cultural heritage sector are necessarily heterogeneous and exhibit a certain resistance to standardisation. Datasheets should therefore, in their function as format templates like the Encoded Archival Descriptions (EAD), be viewed with a certain degree of scepticism, or as two researchers once put it: "Tools and standards are *pharmaka*, giving much but taking as well".¹²³ The datasheets listed below should therefore be regarded as a collection of examples that serve as orientation and support the drafting of datasheets without having to serve as blueprints. Further examples of datasheets from the cultural heritage sector are listed in Fiorucci et al.¹²⁴

Publisher	Description	URL
Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin	Datasheet for the Metadata of the „Verzeichnis der im deutschen Sprachraum erschienenen Drucke“	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15167938
Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin	Datasheet for the Fulltexts of the Digitised Collections of Berlin State Library	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716097
Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin	Datasheet for the Colibri Image Dataset	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15535927
Cultural AI Lab Niederlande	Hugging Face Contentious Contexts Dataset Card	https://huggingface.co/datasets/biglam/contentious_contexts
Melvin Wevers, Nico Vriend, Alexandra Barancová, Jan Kruidhof, Lars Vereecken	De Boer Press Photography Data Sheet ¹²⁵	https://github.com/melvinwevers/HisVis2/blob/main/docs/data_sheet.md

¹²³ Edmond, J., & Lehmann, J. (2021). Digital humanities, knowledge complexity, and the five 'aporias' of digital research. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 36(Supplement_2), ii95–ii108, here p. 100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqab031>.

¹²⁴ Fiorucci, M., Khoroshiltseva, M., Pontil, M., Traviglia, A., Del Bue, A., & James, S. (2020). Machine Learning for Cultural Heritage: A Survey. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 133, 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2020.02.017>.

¹²⁵ Comp. also Brate, R., Nesterov, A., Vogelmann, V., van Ossenbruggen, J., Hollink, L., & van Erp, M. (2021). Capturing Contentiousness: Constructing the Contentious Terms in Context Corpus. *Proceedings of the 11th on Knowledge Capture Conference*, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3460210.3493553>.

Mrinalini Luthra, Konstantin Todorov, Leon van Wissen, Charles Jeurgens, Giovanni Colavizza	Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition ¹²⁶	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129316
British Library	Datasheet for the 19th Century Books Dataset	https://bl.iro.bl.uk/concern/datasets/1e1ccb46-65b4-4481-b6f8-b8129d5da053
Artem Reshetnikov, Maria-Cristina Marinescu, Joaquim More Lopez	Data Card for DEArt: Dataset of European Art ¹²⁷	https://huggingface.co/datasets/biglam/european_art

Summary and Recommendations

These guidelines provide comprehensive guidance for the provision of cultural heritage datasets for AI research. They present a checklist for the publication of cultural data, emphasise the importance of transparent documentation through datasheets and compliance with the FAIR principles, and refer to practical tools and examples for implementing these. Key aspects of dataset creation such as structuring, curation and quality assurance are presented, as are common repositories and the selection of suitable formats and standards.

Recommendations for cultural heritage institutions

- Cultural heritage datasets should be published on publicly accessible platforms, under permissive licences and in compliance with the FAIR principles, in a structured form, equipped with machine-readable metadata and in AI-suitable formats.
- Datasheets should be attached as accompanying publications to the publication of cultural heritage datasets. Ideally, they should be written as part of an interdisciplinary dialogue between domain experts, researchers and technicians, and they should be published in English.
- The creation of datasheets should be integrated into the established procedures and workflows within the respective cultural heritage institution from the outset. Such an approach not only helps to sharpen the criteria for the selection process and the compilation of the dataset, but also enables a transparent and easily comprehensible description for third parties of what is contained in the respective dataset.

Recommendations for funding authorities

- A major obstacle to the provision of AI-enabled cultural heritage datasets is the lack of expertise in cultural heritage institutions with regard to machine learning workflows. However, basic knowledge of these workflows is necessary in order to be able to provide Collections as Data that can be reused by research and development. This knowledge deficit can only partially be compensated for by

¹²⁶ Comp. Luthra, M., Todorov, K., Jeurgens, C., & Colavizza, G. (2024). Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition. *Journal of Documentation*, 80(5), 1080–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-02-2022-0038>.

¹²⁷ Comp. Reshetnikov, A., Marinescu, M.-C., & Lopez, J. M. (2023). DEArt: Dataset of European Art. In L. Karlinsky, T. Michaeli, & K. Nishino (Hrsg.), *Computer Vision – ECCV 2022 Workshops* (Bd. 13801, pp. 218–233). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25056-9_15.

handouts such as this one and self-learning opportunities such as recommended reading. It is recommended that funding opportunities for the creation of advisory services and in-service training (e.g. in interactive workshop formats) be developed to enable managers in cultural heritage institutions in particular to develop expertise in the field of machine learning.

- As the majority of digitisation projects in the Federal Republic of Germany are financed by public funds, data management plans (DMPs) are a regular component of the projects. It is recommended that datasheets become a standard part of such data management plans to ensure high quality data publications.
- The current practice in the development of AI applications is to use all data material available on the internet without regard to the context of origin, copyrights or licences.¹²⁸ It is recommended to work at a political level towards the creation of new licences that regulate such use of publicly funded datasets and to make use of the legal possibilities offered by the Data Governance Act since September 2023.

¹²⁸ Comp. Karamolegkou, A., Li, J., Zhou, L., & Søgaard, A. (2023). Copyright Violations and Large Language Models. *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 7403–7412. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.458>. Paullada, A., Raji, I. D., Bender, E. M., Denton, E., & Hanna, A. (2021). Data and its (dis)contents: A survey of dataset development and use in machine learning research. *Patterns*, 2(11), 100336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100336>.